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Conference Paper · September 2021

DOI: 10.1049/icp.2021.1539

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CONSIDERATIONS ON COMMUNICATING WITH DECENTRALIZED PROSUMER APPLICATIONS THROUGH HOME AREA NETWORK AND WIDE AREA NETWORK

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Keywords: SMART METER INFRASTRUCTURE, WIDE AREA NETWORK, HOME AREA NETWORK

Abstract

The German national implementation of a smart metering infrastructure includes not only the electricity meter but also its own communication device, the smart meter gateway. These devices can provide secured communication channels to other devices for different services, e.g. sub metering, energy trading aspects and tele-control for decentralized energy resources such as photovoltaic systems. The created ICT network ties into the private ICT network of customers. In German national regulation, this network segment is named Home Area Network. The aspect of responsibility for the infrastructure as well as the definition of boundaries of property are critical aspects to be discussed. This contribution structures available implementation options and presents considerations from various research projects, where these systems have been put to the test in a field trial.

1 Introduction

1.1. Smart Meter Infrastructure

The implementation of a Smart Meter Infrastructure (SMI) is a key component in the digitalization of the energy sector and is the foundation for novel operational and economical concepts involving distributed energy resources (DER) [1]. Therefore, this can range from monitoring applications of PV-inverters to billing processes for electric vehicles, and additionally employing novel methodologies such as graph-based distributed ledgers (vulgo Blockchains) [2]. Within this context, the consumer not only consumes but also generates electric energy and will take on a more active role in a future energy system. This is reflected by the new term ‘prosumer’.

The German law on the digitalization of the energy transition [3] introduces a country-specific implementation of such a smart meter infrastructure (SMI). In addition to the electric meter, the systems also contain a communication device called smart meter gateway (SMGW). The SMGW is a combination of data collectors for the electric meter readings and a communication modem, respectively a router, with a highly sophisticated backend system to ensure cyber security. The additional path for the tele-control applications for DER is named by its system category: CLS (Controllable Local System) and

implemented as a separate device which is called CLS-Gateway [4]. This combination of devices is illustrated in the following figure 1.

Fig. 1 One simple SMI modelled in SGAM. Abbreviations are: kWh: electric meter; CLS: controllable local system; SMGW: Smart-Meter-Gateway; GW Admin: Gateway Administrator; ERP: Enterprise Resource Planning; CM: congestion management; CLS Admin: CLS Management and Backend System.

The figure shows the different networks to enforce network separation for the different use cases: Local Metrological Network (LMN), WideAreaNetwork (WAN), HomeAreaNetwork (HAN).

The four binary contacts to codify an active power limitation of 0% / 30% / 60% / 100% stages of nominal power [5] are state-of-the-art for tele-control of decentralized systems in Germany. The manufacturer of PV-Systems have adapted to this and provide a variety of solutions to support this kind of interface. On the Distribution System Operator (DSO) side, the signal source is typically a ripple control device.

The first proposed and defined application of the aforementioned CLS devices is the replacement of this legacy technology. The utilization of more sophisticated technologies such as machine-to-machine communication via a fieldbus protocol like ModbusTCP is one beneficial application. However, it requires the implementation of IP-based communication infrastructure into the domain of the prosumer. When integrating the SMI and CLS devices into an existing HAN for a tele-control application, different use cases must remain possible. This is illustrated in figure 1 for the basic scenario where the Smart Meter (SM) is connected via the LMN and CLS device via the specialized HAN.

1.2. Considered Use Cases

The basic use of the SMI is the implementation of more advanced metering concepts. Such as the reading of energy consumption or generation in 15-min time slices. This metering is a prerequisite to validate the correct function of the following use cases. In this contribution, mainly two functions must be realized in order to satisfy the use cases: tele-control of the DER for the authorized entity, e.g. the DSO, and monitoring of the DER for the prosumer. The PV-system owner might have a vital interest in doing so and continue to do so in the future.

The implementation as it is currently used in the field trial enables the DSO to access a prosumer owned PV-system. The DSO use case utilises an IEC61850-8-1 to ModbusTCP protocol gateway in regards to the SGAM protocol layer. Besides the applied data transmission protocol, a data model conversion from the SunSpec to IEC61850-7-420 was implemented. The US-based SunSpec-Alliance proposed a standardised data model for DER, the national legislation promoted the broad adoption of this protocol in PV-inverters; further details are given in [5]. The protocol gateway, which utilizes this interface, is presented in [6] and is the implemented solution for the discussed applications and its integration on the network architecture in this contribution.

The prosumer use case might be implemented by accessing the PV-system either locally or via a cloud based system – as it is already provided by several manufacturers of PV

inverters. It is expected that connection of the inverter to the manufacturer cloud becomes increasingly more important. Therefore the unrestricted access from the local network to the cloud-based backend system is the key requirement.

1.3. Advanced Use Cases

The CLS-channels enable further grid operation relevant use cases such as the immediate control of PV-systems and e-Mobility limitation in peak hours or the active control of electrical storage heating systems. On the consumer side, PV-self-consumption fosters a wide variation of use cases. These are things like power-to-heat, electro-chemical energy storage systems, etc. Such variety of systems typical need some kind of superimposed control system interacting with the individual subsystems. These kinds of systems are commonly described as Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS) or Consumer Energy Management Systems (CEM). The situation in a more complex installation is shown in figure 2. The starting point of these considerations is the problem arising from the clash of legitimate interests between DSO and grid users.

Fig. 2 Complex SMI & HEMS infrastructure modelled in SGAM with separation of the customer premises in sub-domains. Connections are based on logical affiliation. Abbreviations are: kWh: electric meter; HEMS: home energy management system; LOD: consumer load; HP: heat pump; EVSE: electric vehicle charging; CLS: controllable local system; SMGW: Smart-Meter-Gateway; GW Admin: Gateway Administrator; ERP: Enterprise Resource Planning; CM: congestion management; CLS Admin: CLS Management and Backend System;

One solution is using a cell-based methodology to organise electrical grids and solve the appearing boundary issues at the intersection of electrical grid and buildings. For each entity, its legal or technical requirements must be addressed

and the assignment of responsibility also has to be clarified. Only when these preconditions are fulfilled, a HEMS is able to take action upon encountering conflicts due to boundary issues. The per unit control of a DER in the curtailment use case is superseded by coordinated control of the HEMS to have the same effect to at the boundary to the grid. The active power limitation use case suggested by DKE-VDE-AR 2829-1 is an example for such a system.

More advanced use cases are even more demanding for communication. Ideas such as local energy communities that are enabling automatic electric energy trading within their neighbourhood and ensuring trust by using distributed ledger technology. This requires, in addition to the implementation of the previous use cases, the bidirectional communication between the systems in this community [2].

2. System Architecture

2.1. Frameworks for modelling smart grid architectures

The description of the country-specific implementation for SMI is a complex task. The framework used in this contribution is the Smart Grid Architecture Model [6, 7], which is utilized for the modelling of various applications in the smart grid context [8]. Regarding the model and its corresponding modelling methods, each system is divided in three dimensions:

Interoperability Layer: divides the modelled use case in different levels documenting the legal framework to the the single physical device;

Domain: gives an indication in which sub-domain of the energy sector the proposed system is acting;

Zone: describes the size and area of the system from a single device up to an energy market.

The previously described country-specific use case for the SMI infrastructure is modelled in SGAM and depicted in figure 1. Further frameworks such as Home-and-Building Architecture Model (HBAM) deliver a significant more detailed modelling possibility regarding the customer premises in general, but lack a more detailed representation of energy-related aspects such as grid connection, HEMS, PV and electrical vehicle charging. Applying the basic principal of SGAM domains to the customer premises and introduce sub-domains will result in a more detailed insight in buildings. In figure 2, a separation of the customer premises into such a selection sub-domains is given. This includes the differentiation of components and the respective roles of each component owner. It is obvious that there is a relevant number of property boundaries which must be overcome for an optimal solution and takes into account the individual interests.

2.2. Boundaries of Properties

For the considerations discussed in this contribution, it is necessary to analyze varied situations not only on the technical level but also on the organisation respectively property level. Within the SGAM framework, different entities owning one of the components are mapped into the interoperability layer. The main aspects here are the boundaries between different entities, which can also be understood as the market roles the entities inherit. For a simple situation as found in a single-family house, depicted in figure 1, following boundary lines occur on the electrical grid side with special respect to the national legislation: DSO-to-Owner, Owner-to-Metering Point Operator (MPO), MPO-to-Owner; Owner-to-Manufacturer. In the context of this contribution, these boundaries are abbreviated as BOP (boundaries of property). For complex scenarios, the number of boundaries will certainly increase. Figure 2 shows a more complex situation where the individual market or technical roles are depicted for more complicated application scenarios.

2.3. ICT-components

The proposed architecture of local IPv4-network consists of a standard Class C-network with a standard prosumer grade modem/router combination, which is used by the prosumer for everyday tasks as well as for the monitoring of the PV-inverter via a backend system provided by the manufacturer. This router is also capable to assign new IP-addresses to devices in the network via a DHCP-service. For the tele-control purpose, the CLS-gateway also needs a connection to the PV-inverter in the same HAN as well as a secured secondary connection established via SMGW in opposite direction to the CLS-backend system. In respect of the vague term “the internet”, the consumer router acts as a firewall and restricts the data flow.

Besides routers, ethernet switches (managed & unmanaged switches) may also take over the configuration of network segments and the assignments of IP-addresses via DHCP. When required by specific use cases, an ethernet switch might be helpful to separate the network in sub-domains by dividing the network into tagged VLANs.

3. Implementation Options

When considering integration options for the usage of the SMI / CLS-infrastructure, there are 6 possible variants:

3.1. Default State (A)

If there is no such thing as remote control from the DSO or a SMI schema of the MPO, a typical small-scale prosumer system will comply with the schema depicted in figure 3A). The PV-inverter will connect to the internet via the prosumer’s router by (Wireless)LAN, sending relevant information to some kind of proprietary monitoring systems of the manufacturer. The prosumer can access this system via an app or website.

3.2. SMI Legacy State (B)

The prosumer side remains the same as in the default state. The remote control aspect is implemented via the digital output / digital input connection as shown in figure 3B). This results in two BOPs. One between the SMGW owned by the MPO and the CLS gateway owned by the DSO, where the ethernet cable between the devices is the BOP (cf. B1). The second is the unidirectional digital output to digital input connection between the CLS gateway and the PV inverter owned by the prosumer (cf. B2).

3.3. SMI dominated State (C)

By neglecting the interest of the prosumer with its use case of independent monitoring of the PV system and only focusing on the DSO use case of grid monitoring and curtailment of the PV system the integration of the protocol-based solution can be as depicted in figure 3C). The relevant change in BOP is the replacement of the unidirectional communication with a bidirectional communication based on TCP/IP (cf. C2). In this configuration the CLS gateway can be considered as a perimeter firewall in respect to the SMGW. For the commissioning process the IP-address of the SMGW and the PV-inverter have to match the same subnet and have to be configured respectively defined in the opposing system.

3.4. HAN dominated State (D)

The scenario depicted in figure 3d integrates the SMGW / CLS combination into the standard network of the prosumer. Each device gets an IP address by the DHCP server of the prosumer. The corresponding IP-addresses are configured in the individual devices. There is no network separation in place and no restricted data flow policy can be enforced. As a result, a complex BOP is formed (cf. D1), where the different sub processes use the infrastructure of the prosumer. The key challenge for this configuration scenario is that the field technician installing the systems needs profound knowledge on IT-networks, which is usually not in the scope of a typical electrical technician. Changes in the network made by the prosumer, e.g. replacing the router, might render the configuration useless.

3.5. HAN Client (E)

Integration into the prosumer premises only with one leg of the CLS-gateway. The connection to the backend system is locally and physically separated. In this context the CLS-gateway can be considered as firewall with respect to the SMGW (cf. BOP at E1). The BOP from DSO to prosumer formed by plugging on ethernet port into the prosumer's infrastructure (cf. E2).

3.6. Logical separated network (F)

A further possibility is given by logical network separation on the one side with VLAN separation, if all involved devices are capable of using VLAN (cf. IEEE Std. 802.1Q). With dump switches and devices, the separation as

described in section 3.5 might be achieved by 2 IP addresses for the CLS-gateway in non-overlapping subnets.

Table 1: Comparison of the introduced implementation options

Option	Prosumer Use Case	DSO Use Case	BOP Definable	Req. Skill Level	Vulnerable to hardware change
Default (A)	✓	×	n.a.	•	•
Legacy (B)	✓	✓ (uni)	•	•	•
SMI (C)	×	✓	••	•	•
HAN (D)	✓	✓	•••	••	••
HAN leg (E)	✓	✓	•••	•••	•••
HAN logic (F)	✓	✓	•••	•••	•••

Legend: ✓: realised; ×: not realised; • easily definable / low; •• medium; ••• poorly definable / high

4. Evaluation of implementation options

After defining the different implementation options in the standardised format of figure 3, the suitability for a future smart grid application needs to be discussed. The evaluation takes the following aspects into account: whether the prosumer and the DSO use cases are feasible; whether the boundary of property is definable; the required skill level of the field technician as well as the vulnerability to hardware changes in the HAN. The selected schema ranges from ‘•’ for less favourable and laborious to ‘•••’ for effective and sophisticated solutions. The results of this evaluation are given in Table 1. Options **A** and **C** should be excluded for further discussion, as either the prosumer or the DSO use case is not possible. Option **B** seems favourable but only provides an unidirectional communication in the DSO use case. Options **D**, **E** and **F** tie into the network of the prosumer and are vulnerable to intentional or unintentional manipulation.

5. Conclusion

This contribution can be summarized with two key findings: There is a need for more detailed application guidelines for the Smart Grid Architecture Model methodology on the IT-technical system modelling for a decentralized energy system, especially in consideration of complex SMI and remote-control for billing and grid services. During the transition from a relays-based interface to an IP-based interface, further legislation or technical guidelines are needed to ensure a safe operation and guarantee the protection of the interest of the involved entities. It needs to be further evaluated whether HAN in customer premises has to be considered as an adjacent network used by the MPO and DSO, further actions have to be taken in consideration to mitigate the accrued risks during the utilization of this network. On the other side, the same risk assessment might be considerable for the prosumer regarding the use of interfaces to connect devices provided by the MPO / DSO.

6. Outlook

In the upcoming field trial of the proposed use case the implementation option **D** is chosen due to restrictions of the prototype devices. As shown in section 4, the presented

implementation options are not sufficient and further applied research is planned.

7. Acknowledgements

This contribution presents the results of the project “C/sells” (Grant Agreement No.: BMWi 03SIN136), “SecureEnergyProsumer” (Grant Agreement No. BWSGD 18009 & BWSGD 18011) and “SerendiPV” (Grant Agreement No. 953016).

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